

ROLE OF *MORINGA* IN REGULATING THE KAPHA DOSHA OF THE BODY IN THE
MANAGEMENT OF THE LIFESTYLE DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT

This is the review study about the plant, *Moringa oleifera* (*shighru*, *sobhanjan*) which is now being considered as a superfood due to its multiple health & nutritional benefits. As it belongs to the category of the *katu-tikta rasa* & *ushan-veerya* (hot) plant, it plays a significant role as a *kapha-vata shamak dravya*, beneficial for both the stress & lifestyle (mainly obesity & indigestion related) disorders, healing both in a medicinal way (seeds & roots) & dietary way (as seed pods) in balancing the *Tridoshas* & restoring the health & vitality. It also works as an Anti-Inflammatory, Anti-helminthic, Anti-microbial, Anti-obesity, Digestive for the body by balancing the *Tridoshas* of the body.

KEYWORDS: Agni, Ushan, *katu*, *tikta*, Drum-stick, Health.**INTRODUCTION**

Moringa oleifera, is a very commonly available plant in the India, commonly also known as *Shigru*, *Suhanjana*, *Sobhanjan*, *Sahijana*. Its tree is also known as the Drum stick plant. It belongs to the family *Moringaceae*. As per the Ayurveda, *Moringa* is described as a plant with having the properties to manage the diseases related to the **Vata-kapha dosha** due to its properties. Mostly its root, seed parts are being used in the treatment in the dosage & formulations as prescribed in the Ayurvedic science.

Description

From the Understanding of its properties, its effect on the *kapha dosha* can be understood by the fact that it is having a *katu tikta rasa*, which doesn't favours the formation of the *kapha dosha*, instead it also can mobilise the *amashaya gat* (in abdominal region) accumulated *kapha dosha*, hence clearing it of unwanted materials (post digestive materials & toxins) which may lead to various ailments related to the *Jathragni* like *Agnimandya*.

Similarly, it also leads to the clearing the *rasadi dhatwagni* diseases, which may lead to the conditions like body weakness & other lifestyle related disorders.

Being a *laghu*, *ruksha*, *tikshan dravya*, it pierces the tissues, *dhatu*s & *strotas*, where it clears the accumulated unwanted *kapha dosha* which might be causing *dhatwagini vikars*, accumulation of *aama rasa* & even the conditions of *strotorodh*, which might be creating the condition of blockades, clogging & other related issues in the important *strotas* (channels/arteries or veins).

Being an hot *dravya*, it causes the blocked or less conducting *vata-nadis* (nerves) to conduct the impulses in the proper way by mobilising the *kapha dosha* & hence making it good tonic to relieve the signs of fatigue and general debility.

Due to all these specific actions, *Moringa* is a specific herb which optimises the metabolism of the body, acting as a good purifier of the body from various foreign elements like *krimis*, toxins. Hence, easing the workload of the Liver & improving its overall functions, like managing the Blood cholesterol & triglycerides level. Considering its role in regulating the metabolism within the body, it eliminates the unwanted fat (**Medohar**) stabilising body weight & balancing the body *agnis* & hence improving the digestion of the food in the body.

Hence, being a *kapha & vata dosha* regulator in the body, it also eases the patients of the respiratory ailments like persistent wet cough & respiratory distress related diseases, which may occur due to prolonged deposition of *kapha dosha* in the *pranvaha strotas*.

Hence, easing the heart & lungs from the undue conditions of the distress from these respiratory system.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

As it's clearly being understood from the Ayurvedic texts, that *Moringa* is very beneficial plant in the management of many pathological body conditions. It specific properties which makes it even beneficial in the management of lifestyle disorders are,

- a. Angimandya-har.
- b. Antioxidant.
- c. *Medohar*.
- d. *Kapha dosha* balancer.

Out of these many of its uses, its High-fibre nature makes it suitable for its application among many age groups also, hence its also strengthens the body, while also balancing the *dhatu-gat vikars* of the body.

Due to these, it also controls the body symptoms relating to the conditions of inflammation & the odema of the body in various cardiovascular disorders.

Moringa seed pods, commonly known as Drum-sticks which are relatively sweeter in taste are also being used in the diet by the people.

Due to its immense health benefits, the *Moringa oleifera* is being widely used for the Medicinal use & also a part of the dietary use.

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